
Optical Remote Sensing Lidar in Wind Tunnels

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Creator: Shahbaz Pathan

Affiliation: Danmarks Tekniske Universitet / Technical University of Denmark

Template: H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019

ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2462-5502>

Grant number: 858358

Project abstract:

This PhD project is part of the Lidar Knowledge Europe (LIKE) project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 and led by DTU. Remote sensing using lidars provide an attractive approach to wind energy industries. It is an alternative approach for measurement of wind without disturbing the wind flow. Laser Doppler anemometry, also known as continuous-wave (cw) Doppler lidar, is a well-known technique for measurement of air speed. However, the technique is still challenging in condition of low aerosols. One of the goals of this PhD study is to investigate various signal processing schemes to tackle this issue. Besides investigating signal processing schemes, the goal of this PhD study is also the utilization of continuous wave Doppler lidar in wind tunnels and in connection with wind energy and wind engineering applications. Boundary layer wind tunnels are commonly equipped with one-point observing instruments such as pitot tube and hot wires. The issue with such anemometers is that they are used for single point measurements and we cannot place multiple of these devices for more than one measurement as multiple devices generate disturbance along the flow (Mikael Sjöholm et al. 2017). In order to tackle the issue of multiple point observations and to tackle the issue of disturbance in the way of flow of wind, the optical approaches were used. The traditional approaches are Laser Doppler Velocimetry (LDV) or Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) in wind tunnels. But, the issue with these approaches is that they have very limited range and are not suitable for measuring over larger spatial scales. Due to these issues, the approach of using continuous wave lidars in wind tunnels in order to fill the spatial gap and measure multiple positions in an extremely short time without disturbance is a research area that will be explored in this PhD study. Some scientific activities of this PhD study are development of lidar telescope scanning mechanism, characterization and remote sensing of flow with sampling volumes of a few centimeters.

Last modified: 03-12-2020

Optical Remote Sensing Lidar in Wind Tunnels

Data Collection

Describe the data that will be collected.

This project has been divided into various phases and one of the phases is multiple measurement campaigns and another is analysis of data that will lead to new concepts of wind lidar instruments.

1. Steerable Lidar Data Set

One of the data sets in this project will be collected from experiments with a steerable Lidar. Different data sets will be collected such as data on pure wind and data of different inserted particles. The idea of this data is to develop lidar methods to characterize wind flow.

1. Data from new Danish Poul la Cour aerodynamic and acoustic wind tunnel

Another data set will be collected from the new Danish Poul la Cour aerodynamic and acoustic wind tunnel. The purpose of this data and measurement is to analyse the applications of wind lidar for measuring the wake from wind turbine blades.

1. POLIMI Wind Tunnel

Data will be collected from the POLIMI Wind tunnel. The purpose of these measurements is to demonstrate applications of wind lidar on scaled wind turbines and bridges for collaborating with other LIKE PhD projects.

1. Measurement campaign at Force Technology (Denmark)

Data will be collected from the Force Technology Wind Tunnel. Here, different datasets will be collected for demonstrating the lidar potential in a commercial wind tunnel facility.

Types of data

The datasets will be of the following forms,

1. Raw Lidar Data
2. Post processed Data
3. Instrument control Codes
4. Data analysis Codes
5. Results
6. Conclusions
7. Documents and Reports of every process

Raw Data: Data obtained through Instruments

Post processed Data: Data after applying algorithms

Instrument control codes: Computer Programs for instrumentation setup

Data analysis codes: Computer codes for analysing data

Results and Conclusions: In the form of research journal papers.

Documents and Reports of every process: Metadata along with every dataset about how the things were achieved.

Describe any restrictions to the data.

As one of the goals of this project is to achieve a developed concept of a wind energy applicable instrument with some commercial interactions, some measurement data and detailed methods might be confidential. However, general procedures, results, analysis and conclusion will be published in open access research journals.

Data Storage

Describe the IT infrastructure to be used.

All the data obtained through measurements will be stored on servers and drives hosted at DTU Wind Energy according to the common practice. Access to data will only be provided to people involved in the project during the project but could after the end of the project be accessed for collaborative studies.

Documentation

Describe the metadata to be associated with the data.

While publication of results in research journals, it will be described in papers how the data was achieved and processed. For example, for the steerable lidar dataset, it will be described in the paper how the steering mechanism was done but the details will remain confidential as a default.

Describe the types of documentation that will accompany the data.

Along the data (obtained through experiments), all the details of tools, experiments and the objective of the project will be documented so that data can be reused and could be replicated. With each dataset the detailed description of experiments, algorithms, and procedures will be provided in report form. But, it will be hosted on a DTU server and will not be publically available. Also, all the computer codes developed in this project will be the property of DTU Wind Energy.

Data Sharing

Describe which data will be shared.

The data analysis will be performed in different softwares such as Mathematica, Python, Matlab and signal processing will be done in National Instrument Labview. Results and conclusion will be published in open access research journals. Computer programs will be hosted at DTU servers and can be accessed by relevant people.

Describe how the data will be shared for possible reuse.

The several datasets described in the Data Collection section will be part of DTU Data repository, and each dataset will have its specific metadata description and an access link to the storage server.

Additionally, it will be possible to access all the public material (Open access research papers) through the ORCID ID, Research gate, Google scholar profile of the PhD candidate and authors involved in the papers and partners involved in the project.

Long-term Preservation

Describe how data will be archived beyond the scope of the research project.

The exact amount of data will only be known after the measurements and care must be taken in order to secure the long term preservation of the data.